

Analysis of heavy metals in granulometric fractions and infrared spectroscopic evaluation of bottom sediments in the Damodar river (West Bengal)

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Abstract : Elemental composition of sediments not only depends on anthropogenic and lithogenic sources but also upon the textural characteristics of the sediments. The distribution of Pb, Fe, Mn and Cd in different grain-size fractions and infrared spectroscopic characterization in the bottom sediments of Damodar river has been studied. The most dominant elements in all size fractions at all sites are Fe and Mn followed by Pb and Cd. Study reveals in general that heavy metal tend to be associated with the fine particles of riverine sediments compared to coarser fractions. The concentration of heavy metals of the Damodar river sediments in the study area ranges between 0.105 to 1.452 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Cd), 5.45 to 31.54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Pb), 36.54 to 191.45 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Mn), 115.55 to 412.35 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Fe). Study of FTIR spectrum reveals that the sediment of the study area of river Damodar contains number negative functional groups which can attributed to binding of the metal ions.

Keywords : Damodar river, sediment, heavy metals, granulometric fractions, FTIR.

Introduction

Metals are associated with sediments in aquatic systems largely due to processes of adsorption onto mineral surfaces, absorption into organic matter, ion-exchange in riverine environments. Several environmental pollutants that enter water bodies may remain suspended in the water column, be taken up by aquatic biota, or settle on the bottom and ultimately become incorporated into the sediments¹. Riverine sediment act as a metal pool that can release metals to the overlaying water through natural and anthropogenic processes and pose potential adverse health effects to the ecosystems. Sediments are significant environmental compartment for aquatic system, since they may accumulate contaminants in higher concentration of pollutants than those observed in the water column. Like other toxic pollutants, heavy metals have been of great concern due to their environmental persistence, toxicity, and ability to be incorporated into food chains²⁻⁷. Therefore, assessment of heavy metal in surface sediments is important in order to estimate the extent of pollution or identify pollution sources^{8,9}.

The river Damodar, flows through variable topography and geology, receives substantial amount of pollut-

ants during its flow through the industrial region of West Bengal. During its course it receives effluents from various industries such as iron and steel plant, thermal power plant mainly along its left bank. Heavy metals including different contaminants in the aquatic system can lead to elevated sediment concentrations which ultimately cause potential toxicity to aquatic system and residues may enter the human food chain. Analyses of sediment carried out by various workers¹⁰⁻¹² indicate the metal pollution of the river Damodar. The elemental concentration of sediments not only depends on anthropogenic and lithogenic sources, but also upon the textural characteristics¹³. This work have been undertaken in order to obtain more information regarding the effects of particle size on heavy metal distributions in river sediments. Infrared analyses (FT-IR) were carried out to study the distribution of functional groups in the Damodar river sediments. The infrared spectroscopy finds its greatest utility for identification of organic and organometallic molecules. IR spectroscopy has been used as a holistic tool to investigate the soil chemical properties¹⁴ to measure CH, NH and OH bonds, it is also applicable to the forest soils to determine chemical and biological properties related to soil

sustainability¹⁵ litter quality assessment¹⁶ and analysis of biological materials¹⁷. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy allows the analysis of a relevant amount of compositional and structural information concerning environmental samples¹⁸ the performance of this technique in the studies of complex environmental systems is applied in this study.

Materials and method :

Bottom sediments were collected from 6 different regions from the Damodar river to analyze the heavy metals in granulometric fractions and to identify the functional groups present in the sediment. The deposited sediment samples were collected by scooping with a plastic spade and were placed in plastic containers, and then frozen. Sediment samples were air-dried, ground, and sieved with desire size and further analysis was carried out. For the analysis of heavy metals, 1 g of the sediment samples were digested with 5 : 1 mixture of concentrated HNO₃ and HClO₄¹⁹.

Solution obtained after digestion was filtered (Whatman 42 filter paper), diluted to 25 ml and analyzed through the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC Avanta). The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of river sediment were recorded with Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Model-RX1, spectrometer, USA). The KBr pressed-disc technique is used in this study for preparing a solid sample for routine scanning of the spectra in the in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹.

Results and discussion

Distribution of heavy metals in bottom sediments of river Damodar is represented in Table 1. Heavy metals along with different contaminants in the aquatic system can lead to elevated sediment concentrations which can cause potential toxicity to aquatic biota^{20,21} and ultimately may enter the human food chain^{22,23}. The concentration of heavy metals of the Damodar river sediments in the study area ranges between 5.45 to 31.54 µg/g (Pb), 36.54 to 191.45 µg/g (Mn), 0.105 to 1.452 µg/g (Cd), 115.55 to 412.35 µg/g (Fe). Concentrations of Pb (31.54 µg/g), Cd (1.452 µg/g) and Fe (412.35 µg/g) in the sediments were clearly higher at sampling site S-2 as this site is close proximity to thermal power plants and also in coal mine areas. Among the analyzed heavy metals Fe and Mn are the most dominant elements in all size fractions at all sites, followed by Pb and Cd. The study shows that finer sediments tend to show higher concentrations of heavy metals compared to coarser fractions though it is

Table 1. Distribution of metal concentration in different size fractions

Sites	Size fractions (µm)	Concentration (µg/g)			
		Pb	Mn	Cd	Fe
S-1 Dishergarh	< 75	11.38	155.64	0.545	389.54
	75–250	9.57	78.65	0.212	242.88
	> 250	5.45	43.57	0.145	185.29
S-2 Ramghat	< 75	22.78	122.47	0.708	278.54
	75–250	25.34	86.97	0.854	352.42
	> 250	31.54	74.67	1.452	412.35
S-3 Sillaghat	< 75	12.57	191.45	0.646	335.98
	75–250	10.65	140.98	0.526	275.45
	> 250	9.64	112.35	0.185	155.83
S-4 Gohogram	< 75	11.45	142.52	0.258	406.98
	75–250	10.45	88.24	0.214	375.91
	> 250	8.89	36.54	0.105	264.76
S-5 Barsul	< 75	18.52	112.34	0.842	335.58
	75–250	15.63	102.55	0.621	235.57
	> 250	7.52	88.45	0.423	115.55
S-6 Palla Road	< 75	24.56	142.5	0.626	136.57
	75–250	20.32	136.58	0.545	125.48
	> 250	16.54	122.45	0.318	115.68

not applicable in all the sites and also in all the metals. The higher concentration in the finer fraction is generally due to the increase in specific surface area and to the surface properties of the sediment. The sites S-2 near thermal power plants and coal mining areas the cadmium, lead and iron do not follow the pattern of increasing metal content with decreasing size. The increased concentration of metals in the coarser fractions at this site may be attributed to inputs from the mining and industrial sources. Metal abundance in the river sediment is in the sequence of Fe > Mn > Pb > Cd. The concentrations of Cd exceeded the TEC (Threshold Effect Concentrations), Pb concentration just below the TEC level, while Cd and Pb content were within the recommended PEC (Probable Effect Concentrations) value²⁴.

Infrared analyses (FT-IR) were carried out to study the distribution of functional groups in the Damodar river sediments. The FTIR spectrum of river sediment displays a number of absorption peaks indicating the presence of different types of functional groups. The observed wave numbers with corresponding functional group are presented in Table 2. Analysis of FTIR spectrum of river sediment exhibits the functional group like -OH, -N-H, C-O, C=O, C-Cl, S-H, CO₃²⁻, OH₂, CN, C-Br. The

Table 2. Assignment of the principle descriptive IR absorption bands Damodar river sediments					
Sites	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment			
S-1 Dishergarh	3624.64	-O-H stretching of alcohol and phenol	3624.71	-OH stretching	
	3407.00	-N-H stretching of amine	3426.88	N-H stretching of amide	
	2364.64	C=O group	2371.51	C=O group	
	1627.97	finger print region of C=O, C-O and -OH group	1633.27	carbonate group	
	1033.53	C-O stretching of ether	1031.71	C-O stretching of anhydride	
	774.82	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide	776.91	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide	
	685.31	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide	690.72	C-Cl stretching alkyl halide	
	S-2 Ramghat	3623.92	-O-H stretching of alcohol and phenol	532.45	C-Br stretching alkyl halide
		3429.89	-N-H stretching of amine		
		2364.31	C=O group		
1634.62		finger print region of C=O, C-O and -OH group			
1034.00		C-O stretching of ether			
688.11		C-Cl stretching			
S-3 Sillaghat		3630.25	-O-H stretching of alcohol and phenol		
	3429.00	-N-H stretching of amine			
	2364.14	S-H group			
	1879.72	C=O stretching of acid chloride			
	1627.97	CO ₃ ²⁻ group			
	688.00	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide			
S-4 Gohogram	3756.87	water contaminant			
	3630.25	-O-H stretching of alcohol and phenol			
	3427.34	-N-H stretching of amine			
	2365.51	C=O group			
	1627.97	finger print region of C=O, C-O and -OH group			
	1035.28	C-O stretching of ether			
	778.42	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide			
	690.90	C-Cl stretching of alkyl halide			
S-5 Barsul	3703.08	O-H stretching (free)			
	3450.33	N-H stretching of amine			
	2336.13	CN stretching			
	1876.92	C=O stretching of acid chloride			
S-6 Palla Road	520.27	C-Br stretching of alkyl halide			
	3906.01	OH ₂ stretching			
	3753.85	N-H stretching of amine			

FTIR spectra of the above mentioned studied area shows the presence of negatively charged functional groups like -OH, CO₃²⁻, -Cl, -Br, N-H, C-O etc. Hence the sediments of the studied area have pronounced affinity towards the heavy metal ion binding. The FTIR spectra recorded from the river sediment in the present experiment displayed characteristic absorption band patterns in the frequency range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of more or less similar functional groups.

Conclusions :

Study reveals that heavy metal tend to be associated with the fine particles of riverine sediments due to the relative higher surface area and the compositional characteristics of the fine particles.

Among the studied heavy metals Fe and Mn are the most dominant elements, followed by Pb and Cd, in all size fractions at all sites. The FTIR spectra have exhibited more or less similar spectral features indicating the presence of similar functional groups present in the riverine sediments. The present study reveals that the sediment of the above mentioned area of the river Damodar contains a number negatively charged functional groups which can effectively bind with the metal ions.

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